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A Comprehensive Overview of Tissue Processing Artifacts in Histopathology

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ABSTRACT

Histopathological examination is regarded as the gold standard method for making a definitive diagnosis of a variety of human body abnormalities. However, it is constrained by a number of changes to typical morphological and cytological characteristics brought on by the existence of artifacts. Surgical removal, fixation, tissue processing, embedding, microtomy, staining, and mounting processes can all result in these abnormalities. Therefore, it is crucial to recognize frequently occurring artifacts while interpreting tissue sections histopathologically. The preferred method in histopathology is immunohistochemistry (ICH), which is a crucial auxiliary technique for pathologists in routine diagnostic work as well as in basic and clinical research, including the investigation of biomarkers, since ICH enables confirmation of target molecule expression in the microenvironment.

Immunohistochemistry is a technique that uses antigen-antibody interactions to detect cellular or tissue constituents (antigens). The site of antibody binding is recognized by directly labeling the antibody. The discovery of neoplasms associated antigen has not only made it possible to diagnose human cancer and other diseases more accurately, but it has also illuminated even the most immune-phenotypical heterogeneity of even the most closely related malignancies. Selected groups of target molecules of great significance in cancer biology are discussed. The methods and kinds used in histopathology investigations are described in the article review. Finally, the essay describes the artifacts found during slide evaluation along with the corrective actions.

Keywords:- *Histology, immunohistochemistry, artifacts*

Histopathology,

INTRODUCTION

Histology: In actuality, histology and histopathology are frequently discussed and explained simultaneously. It is impossible to separate the idea of histopathology from histology. Histopathological interpretation requires an awareness of normal histology [4-5]. Histology was a prominent academic field throughout the 19th century and the first half of the 20th century. was a highly fruitful time for the development of new staining methods in histology and histopathology. In fact, in 1906, physiologists in medicine and histology, Camilo Golgi and Santiago Rayman y Cajal, developed new staining methods in histology and histopathology. Golgi was commended for his staining methods and Cajal for his accurate hypothesis [6]. Histology is the study of the microscopic features and structure of cells and their tissues using a light, fluorescence, or electron microscope, or by looking at a slice that has already been created using the proper methods known as histological techniques. The use of fixatives has been studied by several histopathologists over the years. Formalin was first widely employed in 1893, and it is still widely used today. Histological structures are frequently used to modify or increase the color of specific biological kinds that differ from those that may be found adjacent to them in order to understand distinct biological structures [7].

Histopathology: The study of biological tissue and cells with their microscopic alterations or abnormalities that may be the cause or effect of disease is known as histopathology. The primary use of histopathology in clinical medicine is the biopsy, which is a surgical procedure in

which a pathologist takes a sample from a patient for diagnosis or assessment. The pathologist is more appropriately called a histopathologist (the specific pathologist's job is to examine sick tissue under a microscope). Enzyme histochemistry, electron microscopy, and polarization microscopy have all developed into diagnostic techniques during the past 50 years. Johannes Muller wrote the first book on the specialization of histological method, *The nature and structural characteristics of the cancer*, in 1838. The diagnosis of cancer has been transformed by the use of immunochemistry, which is still being developed with new antibodies and biomarkers that were first discovered in the 1980s. The mid-1900s saw a number of changes in histology labs. The advent of immunohistochemistry in the 1980s revolutionized histopathology techniques [8,9] and rendered them obsolete due to the need for electronic devices. In histopathological investigations, a number of new techniques were developed, including flow cytometry, FISH (fluorescence in situ hybridization), DNA and genetics techniques, proteomics, telepathology, and digital imaging.

Immunohistochemistry: This method uses antigen-antibody interactions to detect cellular or tissue components (antigen). The location of anti-body binding can be found using either direct antibody labelling or secondary labelling techniques. Immunohistochemistry has developed into a powerful tool in the toolbox, even if histological examination of hematoxylin and eosin-stained tissue sections is still the mainstay of head and neck surgical pathology practice [10]. ICH gets its name from the roots of immune, which refers to the antibiotics employed in the operation,

and histo, which means tissue. In 1941, Albers Coons conceived and carried out the method in ICH [11]. Physicians utilize ICH Toxins, viruses, bacteria, and other foreign particles are examples of antigens that can be used to detect the presence of certain antigens in cells [12]. Immunofluorescence (fluorophore-labelled) immune-peroxidase antibodies are used in immunohistochemical staining techniques to detect proteins and other cell molecules.

Purpose of Immunohistochemistry:

Doctors utilize ICH to detect the presence of certain antigens on cells, such as toxins, bacteria, viruses, etc. Many cancer cell types have antigens on their surface that scientists refer to as tumor-specific antigens, which can assist identify the sort of cancer or disease it is. ICH is also utilized to identify various diseases associated with macromolecular structures and proteins [13,14].

How Does Immunohistochemistry Works:

Your immune system produces antibodies, but scientists create the antibodies for ICH staining in a lab. Antibodies are molecules that firmly bind to antigens, and ICH employs them to identify antigens. The pathologist uses dye to create a particular antibody, which activates the dye when the antibody attaches to the antigen. This procedure known as staining. A sample of tissue from a biopsy is taken by the pathologist. They will use antibodies to examine the tissue sample and use a microscope to check for dye activation. ICH staining helps pathologists diagnose patients accurately by identifying the precise antigen present [15,16,17]. Because it permits a comparatively large number of enzyme molecules, like peroxidase, to connect to the antigen site, this system tends to be very sensitive. The colour of reaction is determined selection of precipitating chromogen usually

diaminobenzidine(brown) or aminoethyl carbazole(red)[18]

Sample Visualization:

Depending on the antibody detection technique, the samples are examined using either light or fluorescence microscopy after the sections are ready. Confocal microscopy can be used to improve imaging capabilities and obtain more information. Additionally, high content screening can be used to quickly quantify and compare data from several samples [19, 20]

Artifacts:

Pathologists frequently come across slides that have either been incorrectly fixed during tissue processing, changing the features of the tissue. These modifications are categorized as artifacts. "Artifacts" refers to tissue changes caused by unrelated factors on a prepared microscopic slide [21].

Classification of Artifacts [22]:

- Prefixation artifacts
- Fixation artifacts
- Artifacts related to bone tissue
- Tissue-processing artifacts
- Artifacts related to microtomy
- Artifacts related to floatation and mounting
- Staining artifacts
- Mounting artifacts

Prefixation artifacts: There are several kinds of prefixation artifacts that are created prior to tissue being repaired, including the following:

Artifact of injection

Avoid injecting anesthetic fluid intralesionally as this may result in bleeding due to extravasation and the separation of connective tissue bands due to vacuolization.[23, 24] For instance, bulla formation in gingival disease or edema can cause confusion when

diagnosing Crohn's disease or orofacial granulomatosis [25].

Squeeze artifact

Minimal compression by forceps or other surgical instruments can cause tissue distortion, such as splits, fragmentation, crush bleeding, and pseudo-cysts. [23, 24] Under a microscope, crush artifacts show deformed, darkly stained nuclei and unrecognizable cellular features. By inserting a suture inside the mucosa to be excised and gripping its ends using artery forceps, this can be prevented.[25]

Falgaration artifact

A zone of heat necrosis and tissue distortion results during electrosurgical or laser tissue cutting. Because of protein coagulation, the connective tissue and epithelium seem amorphous. The nuclei take on a spindled, palisading shape, and the epithelial cells seem to be separated from the connective tissue. By retrieving the specimen using the cutting electrodes rather than the coagulation electrodes, this can be avoided.[22]

Artifact of starch

Cytological and histological specimens are frequently contaminated by starch powder, a surgical glove lubricant. They show up as numerous blue, tiny, spherical structures in secretions stained with hematoxylin and eosin. They appear as refractile, glassy, polygonal masses in oral cystomear that range in diameter from 5 to 20 μm . They have a center dot or Y-shaped structure that could be mistaken for a pyknotic nucleus or a cell going through mitosis. These may also be similar to epithelial cells. They have a "Maltese cross" birefringence pattern under polarized light microscopy and are periodic acid Schiff (PAS) positive.[26]

Autolysis Artifact

To avoid enzyme loss, mitochondrial damage, RNA and protein degradation,

and a reduction in mitosis due to the resulting anoxia, tissues should ideally be restored right away and entirely from the live condition. Due to the loss of normal basophilia caused by RNA in the cytoplasm, increased eosin binding to denatured intracytoplasmic proteins, and cytoplasm vacuolization, autolyzed tissue exhibits enhanced eosinophilia. Pyknosis, karyolysis, and cryopexies are examples of nuclear alterations.[27]

Formalin pigments are fixation artifacts

Formic acid is naturally produced when formaldehyde is oxidized. Therefore, formalin and red blood cells combine to generate the formalin-heme complex, which manifests as brown-black amorphous to microcrystalline granules in tissue secretions.

The pigment shares many physical and histochemical characteristics with other pigments and is derived from hematin. Immersion in saturated alcoholic picric acid removes them from tissue secretion. This issue will be reduced by using buffered neutral formalin [29].

Pigments containing mercury

Although fixative is present in mercuric chloride, dark brown granular deposits are not always produced. Alcoholic iodine therapy can eliminate these extracellular pigments [29].

The fixative solution's osmolality Whereas isotonic (300–320 mOsm) fixative solutions cause cellular shrinkage, hypertonic fixative solutions increase extracellular gaps. A slightly hypertonic solution (400–450 mOsm) produced the best results.[30]

Artifact of ice crystals

It is the outcome of tissue freezing slowly. Improper quenching or a tissue sample that is too big to be frozen quickly. It manifests as intracellular clefts and vacuoles in

skeletal muscle and intercellular clefts in highly cellular tissue.[31]

Freezing artifact

Appear in tissue and epithelial gaps as Swiss cheese holes. They depict regions where the tissue is ruptured by ice crystals. In biopsies, this osmotic damage from ice formation in fixative solution is typically administered.[23]

Streaming artifact

This is because unfixed material diffuses and ends up somewhere other than its original location, giving false localization. It is most frequently observed in tissue that has been treated with formalin. Freeze drying or the use of glycogen fixatives can prevent it.[30]

Microwave fixation artifact

Optimum temperature for microwave fixation is 45°C-55°C. Overheating produces vacuolation, overstrained cytoplasm and pyknotic nuclei.[30].

ARTIFACTS RELATED TO BONE TISSUE

Artifacts made of bone dust

When a portion of bone with undecalcified resin is sliced, dust is created. While some of these pieces are deposited on the sliced surface, others might be inserted deeper into the specimen. It has a prominent hematoxylin stain in the segment stained with hematoxylin and eosin. It originates from calcified trabecular matrix because it stains black with von Kossa when deposited in bone marrow. After sawing, it's occasionally advised to use a soft brush to carefully clean the block's surface of debris. [32]

Decalcification When tissue is unfixed or partially fixed, acid-decalcifying fluids' hydrolytic effects can accelerate the digestion of cellular and other tissue components. It mostly affects tooth enamel. By carefully fixing the specimen

before decalcification, this can be decreased.[33]

Excessive decalcification

There is a noticeable decrease of nuclear basophilia and a significant eosin stain. The cytoplasmic and nuclear details are not well retained. Fixation of the specimen prior to decalcification and radiographic monitoring of the decalcification's progress and completion can lessen the harmful effects of acid decalcifying solution [32].

Artifacts from tissue processing:

Inadequate dehydration

Shrinking artifacts are high levels of tissue shrinking caused by prolonged exposure to increased alcohol concentrations. Vacuolization occurs when the tissue is macerated for an extended period of time in a reduced alcohol dilution. Additionally, these two processes will interfere with the staining capabilities and cause the tissue to become brittle. When this happens, rehydrate the tissue portion and carry out the processing again [34,35]. Dehydration should always be applied gradually, beginning at 50%.[36]

INADEQUATE CLEARANCE

Extended exposure to xylene will cause the tissue bottle to crumble and crystallize while being cut. If the specimen is not well cleaned in xylene, the paraffin will not impregnate correctly and the tissue will be distorted during sectioning.[36] Incorrect embedding

When a specimen is exposed for an extended period of time during the embedding process, it becomes friable due to excessive hardening, and sectioning will result in cracks [34].

AN ARTIFACT OF ORIENTATION

A slide with improper orientation will have haphazardly placed histological features. In order for all strata to be visible on the final slide, the skin must be oriented so

that the epithelial borders, subcutaneous tissue, and deeper layers are all flat to the bottom. In order for the cut section to accurately depict the submitted tissue, all of the tissue fragments should be securely lodged in the bottom of the container when embedding more than one specimen. [22] Soluble material loss.

Fat solvents are used in the manufacture of paraffin wax, cellulose nitrate, and the majority of synthetic resin embedded sections. As a result, when adipose tissue is processed, fat dissolves from fat cells and appears as ovoid gaps encircled by cytoplasm, such as lipomas [22].

MICROTOMY-RELATED ARTIFACTS

Sections with tears and scores

These are brought on by a nick or flaw in the knife's edge, as well as by sectioning hard objects like calcification foci and block debris. In the former case, the tear typically covers the entire region. Resharpener or using a different knife part is avoided. In the latter case, it might begin there. It can be prevented by using a tiny, sharp-pointed scalpel to remove the hard particle, re-embedding in freshly filtered wax, or decalcifying the surface before cutting [37].

Conversations

Thick and thin areas parallel to the knife edge are referred to as chatters. Chatters/Venetian blind artifact. Thick and thin areas parallel to the knife edge are referred to as chatters.[38]

ARTIFACT OF COMPRESSION

1. Blunt knife: It is frequently observed that tissue components, particularly bone, are displaced.
2. The knife's bevel is too wide; either reground or resharpen to create secondary bevels.

3. Wax too soft or tissue or sectioning problem. Use a greater melting point or use ice to cool the block.

It happens as a result of overly rough pruning of the thicker paraffin blocks. In the next thin sections with their long axis parallel to the knife edge, the tissue fragments that are pulled out of the block face appear as voids or holes. Regular sharpening of the knife and rough cutting at a lower thickness setting are necessary to prevent these artifacts.[37]

FLOATER ARTIFACT

Tissue fragments that don't belong on slides are known as floaters. They might have floated during processing as a result of careless cutting bench operations involving soiled towels, knives, and gloves, as well as inadequate cleaning before moving on to the next case. [36]

Switch between parts that are thick and thin. When the wax is too soft for tissue, the block or blade is loose, the clearance angle is inadequate, or the microtome mechanism is malfunctioning, alternating thick and thin sections are created. The solution is to raise the clearance angle, tighten the blade, and use ice to chill the block (37). Additionally, tissue may start to wrinkle and curl at this point.

ITEMS PERTAINING TO MOUNTING AND FLOATING

Sections floating on the water bath for an extended period of time

Tissue may enlarge beyond its initial dimensions, deform, and give the epithelium an acantholytic look that resembles edema [30].

WRINKLES AND FOLDS IN THE SECTION

When extremely thin paraffin sections are forced to stretch unevenly against other structures with differing consistencies, tissue sections wrinkle and fold.

These artifacts show up as strands with deeper stains. Stretching and gentle forcep tapping can be used to eliminate any last creases and fords in the water bath portion. Overstretching during these techniques may result in a tear in the tissue section, giving the epithelium an acantholytic look. (30, 36)

POLLUTION

Dust, hair, and leftover cells from the preceding stage may occasionally pollute the water bath. It has been demonstrated that using fingers to remove air bubbles, sneeze, or cough can result in contamination with squamous epithelial cells and keratinous debris. [39] False-positive For floating parts, iron in the tap water has been linked to Prussian blue reactions. [30]

BUBBLES OF AIR

Air bubbles may form beneath the tissue sections as they float in the water bath. Collapsed bubble artifacts are caused by air bubbles trapped beneath the sections collapsing, creating broken areas that, when dry, do not adequately adhere to the glass slide and exhibit changed staining. Using freshly heated water in a flotation bath can help avoid this. [40]

ARTIFACTS STAINED

Wax residue

Parts of a slice will have incomplete or partial staining if the wax is not removed before staining. The pink illness artifact may arise from this. Nedzel et al. conducted a thorough analysis of this item in 1951. Internuclear birefringent inclusions were reported by this author, especially in lymphocytes. [41]

ARTIFACTS CAUSED BY ADDING ACETIC ACID TO EOSIN

Acetic acid can sometimes improve eosin staining by increasing the depth of coloration because it increases the ionization of tissue amino groups, which

leads to more dye adhering. When too much acetic acid is applied, a deep pink-stained mass that is undifferentiated, uniform, and flat results [30].

ARTIFACT BROUGHT ON BY HEMATOXYLIN MORDENT

Many hematoxylin products contain aluminum potassium sulfate as a mordent. Inadequate mixing of the hematoxylin solution during staining leads to the conversion of aluminum potassium sulfate to crystalline form, which deteriorates the solution and causes a black pigment to emerge across the section. This pigment, known as hematin, precipitates because there is no mordent. [35] Artifacts caused by hematoxylin's fluorescent shine.

Sometimes the surface of an active alum hematoxylin solution takes on a luminous sheen. The final slide will show sheets or clumps of dye particles if this fluorescent sheen is not adequately eliminated. [35].

MOUNTING ARTIFACTS

Residual water and air bubbles

Air bubbles are formed under the coverslip when the mounting medium is too thin and as it dries, more air gets sucked under the edges. This can be prevented by using mounting medium of adequate thickness and removal of air bubbles from under the slide. [22]

DRY MOUNTING ARTIFACTS

The slides should not be allowed to dry during the application of coverslip. An artifact with the following three distinct features can be produced.

A. Section may exhibit brown stippling which resembles pigment highly refractile lines outlining cells and tissue.

B. Trapped air may be seen in the nuclei leading to dark nuclei lacking details (corn-flake artifact).

This artifact can be corrected by removing coverslip in xylene and placing in xylene for few minute and then remounting before drying the slide.

Artifacts related to excessive use of mounting media excessive use of mounting media or the mounting media will result in foggy appearance. This artifact can be prevented by using adequate amount of mounting media with proper consistency.[30]

**MOLECULAR MARKER
DESCRIPTION**

- i. Epithelial marker: keratins
- ii. General mesenchymal markers: vimentin
- iii. Muscle markers: desmin, actins, myoglobin's, myogenic
- iv. Neural markers: S100, GFAP, neurofilaments, CD57
- v. Endothelial markers: CD31, CD34, factor VIII related antigen
- vi. Lymphoid markers: κ and λ , CD3, CD15, CD20, CD30, CD45, CD68, CD79a, ALK-1 and TdT
- vii. Neuroendocrine markers: synaptophysin, chromogranin
- viii. Metastatic tumor markers: CK7, CK20 and villin
- ix. Minor salivary gland tumor markers: S-100 protein, actins[43,44,45].

APPLICATION

In cases of unclear tumors, IHC is a helpful supplement to H&E diagnosis, confirming H&E section impressions or establishing conclusive diagnoses. It is especially helpful in differentiating hematolymphoid neoplasms and carcinoma from lymphoma and melanoma. Determining whether genetic mutations are present.

Determining whether chromosomal translocation is present.

To determine the cancer treatment target IHC tests are required for the diagnosis of soft tissue neoplasms such as round cell tumors, monomorphic spindle cell tumors, epithelioid soft tissue cancers, and pleomorphic spindle cell tumors.

Malignant round cell tumor diagnosis [46, 47].

CONCLUSION

Although IHC can be a challenging method to master, a sound positive result supported by suitable controls is ultimately compelling proof of the expression of a specific protein in a tissue sample as well as, crucially, the location of that protein. Even the most advanced microscope cannot produce a high-quality image from a poorly stained sample, hence the preparation of a well-stained sample is crucial to the outcome. Perhaps the oldest technology still widely used in contemporary biomedical research is microscopy.

Microscopy is still a crucial research tool for locating the expression of molecules and molecular complexes, even though molecular biology has provided science with amazing tools and insights into cellular mechanisms in health and illness.

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